

Style in Eight Syllables

Metric Annotation and Stylometry of Chrétien de Troyes and Contemporaries

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Prosodic annotation for the attribution of Medieval texts

Known to increase attribution performance of verse (and even prose) texts
cf. Plecháč and Birnbaum, 2023.

More stable authorial features for medieval texts?

(*ChevLyon*, v. 3501)

H **Chiet** del **fuerre** si li **apointe**

V **Chiet** dou **fuerre** et si **apointe**

F **Cait** a **tere** si li **apointe**

R **Kiet** del **fuerre** si que li **pointe**

- **Graphemic and lexical variation** (incl. FW)
- **but identical prosodic pattern** (SwWswwwS) (slightly more robust than rhyme word)

Case study: the attribution of the works of Chrétien de Troyes

The case in 30 seconds

Chrétien de Troyes (c. 1130 – † b. 1180 and 1190), most canonical 12th cent. French writer, and ‘introducer’ of the Grail;

Collaborative authorship *Lancelot* (with. Godefroi de Leigny)

Dubious attributions *Philomena* (*Crestiens li gois*), Guillaume d'Angleterre (*Crestiens*); Continuations to Perceval;

Case study: the attribution of the works of Chrétien de Troyes

Last year's results

Follow-up to: Camps et al., *The Authorship of the Works of Chrétien de Troyes: A Stylometric Examination*, **DHBenelux 2024**.

Main conclusions:

- Lancelot: drop in Chrétien's style around v. 6150, consistent with intervention of Godefroi de Leigny;
- Perceval: new drop towards the end (possible unknown collaborative authorship or artefact?)
- Guillaume d'Angleterre and Philomena: mixed results.

Question: Could rhythm-based patterns perform better than (and/or improve the attribution accuracy of) function words?

2024 Results: Lancelot

2024 Results: Perceval

Outline

- 1 Metric annotation of Old French romances
- 2 Benchmarking function words and prosodic features
- 3 Results and discussion

Verse types and Metronome annotation pattern

The narrative octosyllabic couplet

- 8 syllable long
- rhymed two by two
- masculine or feminine rhyme
- no standard caesura

Metronome annotation (Nagy et al., 2024)

w weak syllable

S stressed syllable

. word break

Verse	Annotation
et li chevax tant s'esforça	w.w.wS.w.wwS
Et a la pierre de l'anel,	w.w.w.Sw.w.wS

Word breaks were removed for analysis, as they decrease SVM performance

Automated annotation: LLMs vs rule-based

Two approaches

LLMs chain-of-thought; prompting with examples, and a set of expert rules;

Rule based deep-learning for linguistic annotation (POS, lemmas) + rule-based syllabification and stress annotation (using phonological knowledge).

Steps

- ① linguistic annotation (rule based only): POS tagging to find function words;
- ② syllabification;
- ③ identification of stressed/unstressed syllables.

Syllabication by rules

Each verse is processed letter by letter using the following rules:

- Basic Rules:
 - Automatic addition of consonants to the current syllable.
 - Addition of vowels followed by the termination of the vowel.
- Complex Rules:
 - If the last syllable of a word contains only consonants, it is attached to the preceding syllable.
 - If the analyzed vowel and the following vowel form a diphthong that does not end in 'e', both are added to the current syllable.
 - If the analyzed vowel and the following vowel form a diphthong that ends in 'e', it is checked whether the 'e' is at the end of the word; if so, it is separated into its own syllable.
 - Unknown characters are removed.
 - Apostrophes are treated as consonants

Results of annotation

- LLMs performed well on syllabification (≥ 0.95), but poorly on stress identification (0.7827 with Claude 3.5).
- Rule-based approach obtained the best results (accuracy 0.9787).

(Levenshtein ratio: $1 - (\text{Levenshtein distance}_{i,j} / \text{len}_i + \text{len}_j)$)

Code: <https://github.com/PoidsPlume/AnoChre>.

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Setup

Features

- function words;
- prosodic:
 - n-grams of syllables;
 - n-grams of verses.

Training

- SVM Linear classifier
- 375 verses samples (\approx 3000 words)
- group-k-fold cross-validation
- downsampling (for imbalance)
- culling at different %ages

Benchmark results

Feats	n	culling	F1 score
<i>funct. words</i>	1	0.1	<i>0.86</i>
met. syll.	11	0.6	0.88
met. lines	1	0.3	0.75
funct. words	1	0.6	0.95
+ met. syll.	9	0.7	
funct. words	1	0.4	0.97
+ met. lines.	1	0.9	

Summary

- taken alone, prosodic features perform **comparably to FW**;
- in combination, **can improve substantially the scores**.

Culling and n-gram size (prosodic feats)

F1-score as a function of N-gram and Culling

F1-score as a function of both Culling

Syllables n-grams length versus culling (left) and culling of function words versus of full verses (right).

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Lancelot

Rolling Stylometry Decision Functions Over Lancel-1.xml

Same drop around v. 6150.

Perceval (FW, met. syll.)

Rolling Stylometry Decision Functions Over Percev.xml

Perceval (FW, met. line)

Last year's blip towards the end in Chrétien's style disappeared. . .

First Continuation

Coefficients

Coefficients for GerbM

Coefficients for ChrTr

Discussion

Main conclusions

- ① Prosodic features function reasonably well in isolation, and can improve substantially the baseline results (function words) for Old French verses;
- ② features most efficient in isolation are not necessarily the most useful in combination (need to bring additional information);
- ③ collaborative status of Lancelot again confirmed?
- ④ status of Perceval: blip disappears with best features;
- ⑤ (highly culled) prosodic features seem to give an advantage to Chrétien (more distinct style?).

More research needed

- surprising behaviour of culling at different levels;
- authorship verification approach needed with the new features (e.g. impostors).

Thanks

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Outline

4 2025

5 2024

Guillaume d'Angleterre

Rolling Stylometry Decision Functions Over GuillAngl.xml

Philomena

Rolling Stylometry Decision Functions Over Philom.xml

Philomena

Rolling Stylometry Decision Functions Over Philom.xml

First Continuation

Outline

4 2025

5 2024

2024 Results: Lancelot

2024 Results: Perceval

2024 Results: Philomena

Philom

2024 Results: Guillaume d'Angleterre

GuillAngl

